

ISic3278

I.Sicily inscription 3278

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---][D]onatia [---]
2. [---][vi]xit ann[is][---]
3. [dep(osit)][---No]n(as) Mar[t(ias)---]
4. [---consul]atu dd(ominis) [nn(ostris)---]
5. [--- Hon]o[r]io [---]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (eng)

Donatia...lived for [?] years...placed...Nones of March...in consular year of our masters...Honorius...

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493986

EDR 138759

EDCS 22200407

Bibliography

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 166

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